

The Political Expediency of Counter-Disinformation: An Analysis of the Response to Russian Information Warfare

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Abstract

The Russia Federation has, for several decades, been involved in an information war with NATO that has escalated in recent years. However, Western responses to these operations themselves constitute a form of information warfare that employ similar tactical use of disinformation, manipulation, and propaganda. While Russia may be guilty of various crimes, failure to fully disclose Western capabilities and activities in this field have led to the establishment of a narrative within which Russia is the sole perpetrator of unethical and unlawful acts. By analyzing the purported activities of the Russian Federation and the nature of Western responses, this paper shows that conflict in the information sphere is a far more balanced and nuanced affair than is often presented in Western media discussion of the subject.

Keywords: Propaganda, Disinformation, Information Warfare, Russia, RussiaGate

I. Introduction

The collective West, which we will consider here as the member states of the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO), has been engaged in a decades-long information war with first the USSR, and later the Russian Federation. This conflict entered a more intense phase following the 2016 US presidential election, when the victory of Donald Trump was attributed, in part, to interference by the Russian government. Numerous books promoted the message that Russia's information operations had become an existential threat to Western democracies (Rychalk and Pacepa, 2013; Soldatov and Borogan, 2017; Benkler and Roberts,

2018; Watts, 2018; Carlin, 2019; Pomerantsev, 2019; Stengel, 2019), as did several reports from academic groups focusing on the issue of online manipulation (Ajir and Vailliant, 2018; Hindman and Barash, 2018; Mazarr et al., 2019; Meserole and Byman, 2019; Nembr and Gangware, 2019). The most common claims focused on alleged Russian interference in the 2016 US election and the UK's Brexit referendum of the same year (Watts, 2018, 139; Zakem et al, 2018, 27; Nembr and Gangware, 2019, 14).

There is no question that Russia engages in information warfare, all states do to varying extents, and Russia has a long history of both developing effective propaganda (Kenez, 1985) and carrying out high-level intelligence opera-

tions (Suvorov, 1984). The more important questions are whether the threat posed by Russian activities was as significant as claimed, whether Russia was engaging in activities which Western states did not, and whether these allegations were being used to advance other agendas. This paper contends that the extent of Russian activities was significantly exaggerated, that the West was conducting its own, aggressive information warfare of similar form, and that the purported ‘Russian threat’ was used to promote partisan and censorious control of online information under guise of ‘safe-guarding democracy’. The paper will first examine the elements of Russia disinformation and the accuracy of how this is reported in the West, then look at the network of Western experts working in this field, next at the specific case of RussiaGate, then at how similar operations by other states are treated, and finally at the way Western technology companies are responding to these perceived threats. From this, the paper will show how information operations by one state invariably become distorted by the reactive operations of other states and thus highlight the importance of maintaining a neutral perspective, one which analyzes the active and reactive information operations of all parties to a conflict.

II. Russian Disinformation

It should be made clear that the intent of this paper is not to suggest that Russia is uninvolved in the spread of disinformation. It would be absurd to expect any state involved in great power politics to refrain from the use of propaganda and other manipulative acts. The issue is whether Russia is an exceptional case, or, whether efforts to portray this as being true are part of a campaign of memetic warfare, the “branch of information war that seeks to use the tools of propaganda to instill narrative beliefs within a target population for political purposes.” (Gray, 2021, 14) These ‘memetic narratives’ frame public understanding of complex

issues in a simplified manner that allows easy and rapid transmission of a less nuanced, more partisan interpretation of events. In this case, the key narrative being that ‘Russia lies’.

Certainly, Russia engages in both propaganda and disinformation and, with skills honed throughout the Cold War, it has considerable aptitude for both. However, in this it is no different to its numerous Cold War adversaries who gained similar skillsets. It is also important to note the significant difference in acts directly orchestrated by the Kremlin, and inaccurate or deceptive statements from other sources which simply support Russian positions. This difference can be seen through examination of the EUvsDisinfo website.

The site is, “the flagship project of the European External Action Service’s East StratCom Task Force,” and a branch of the European Union’s diplomatic service (EEAS, 2020a). Its stated goal is to catalogue examples of Russian disinformation and claims to have more than 17000 cases in its database. However, analysis of even a small sample suggests that its methodology is questionable. It should be noted that the following four examples are purely the first four stories on the site which were chosen and are far from an extensive analysis, which would be far beyond the scope of this paper. The first examines an incident in which a ten-year-old girl was reportedly killed in shelling from Ukrainian forces. A BBC reporter traveled to the area looking for confirmation but could find none, they then heard from a Russian reporter that the girl didn’t exist and that the Russian team had reported it simply because they “had to”. However, EUvsDisinfo presents this as the BBC reporter making “the actual authors of the false news story confess to the camera that they had lied.” (EEAS, 2017), which is not precisely correct. The Russian stations reported information given to them by a commander of the Donetsk People’s Republic militia, without verifying the information’s accuracy, which suggests that the “authors” of the statement were the militia

rather than Russian networks. Additionally, the BBC reporter questions an unidentified, allegedly Russian, journalist who says the death did not happen. This does not constitute ‘proof’ that no death occurred. The BBC report also fails to mention that in 2015 hundreds of civilians were killed by artillery fire in the Donetsk and Luhansk regions, many of them undoubtedly children (HRW, 2015). Nevertheless, it appears to at least constitute an example of Russian media promoting stories with questionable sourcing. A similar example, and what they call, “one of the peaks of the Kremlin-orchestrated campaign,” involved claims of Ukrainian troops crucifying a young child (EEAS, 2016). Once again, the story appears to have no evidence beyond the claims of a single person, which again points to a willingness of Russian news services to present rumor as fact, so long as it serves the narratives they wish to support. Even so, there is no evidence that these lies are being directly fabricated by the Russian state or its media.

While these do provide evidence of Russia promotion of propagandistic narratives, they are no more damning than US media’s widespread acceptance of fabricated stories such as that of ‘Nurse Nayirah’ which helped launch the 1990 Gulf War (Walton, 1997, 772), or the ‘heroic’ rescue of Jessica Lynch from the 2003 Iraq War (Kampfner, 2003). Other examples from the site suggest, however, that not all their cases are as reasonably classifiable as disinformation. One cites a reporter on a Russian TV network, claiming that “Ukraine is a US client state,” and arguing that this was why the US media did not critically analyze Ukrainian affairs (EEAS, 2020b). A simple reference to another country being a “client state” qualifies the article as disinformation despite this being a purely subjective term. It seems unlikely the EU would have considered it part of a disinformation campaign when The National Interest referred to Serbia as a Russian client state (Merry, 2016), when the Guardian referred to Kyrgyzstan in the same way (Ott,

2014), when USA Today referred to Syria similarly (Robbins, 2015), or when President Obama referred to Ukraine itself as a Russian client state (Iakubovych, 2016).

Another example of purported disinformation is taken from an American online article that spends 1300 words criticizing President Trump’s handling of the Covid crisis (EEAS, 2020c). From this, a single sentence saying that the virus may have been engineered rather than natural is used to label the piece as Russian disinformation (Butler, 2020). Nothing in the article mentions Russia, yet, merely holding such an opinion is deemed enough to mark the author as an agent of the Kremlin even though similar views appeared have appeared in numerous US newspapers including the highly respected New York Times (Gertz, 2020; Chan, 2024). A possible reason for focusing on this specific author’s work as ‘disinformation’ lies in the fact that he was previously the author of a book denouncing anti-Russian Western propaganda (Butler, 2017), suggesting partisan standards being used by EUvsDisinfo. While the site doubtless contains numerous examples of verifiable Russian disinformation, even this brief analysis shows clear evidence of bias in its methodology and the use of an overly loose definition of what constitutes ‘disinformation’.

That Russia and Western states will be treated differently is predictable given that many of those examining the topic openly admit to perceiving a fundamental difference between the two. Watts states that, in contrast to Russia, the USA stands for, “freedom, liberty, human rights and peaceful protest.” (2018, 189) Singer and Brookings, meanwhile, profess that the West is at a disadvantage because, “shaped by the enlightenment, they seek to be logical and consistent. Built upon notions of transparency, they seek to be accountable and responsible.” (2019, 211) The danger posed by Russia is presented as, “a system of mind manipulation that authoritarians now duplicate, and, if left unchecked will be used by authoritarians everywhere to overwhelm democratic audiences

with waves of conflicting information.” (Watts, 2018, 19)

One theme of this narrative is that Russia is, in the words of the commander of NATO, engaged in, “the most amazing information warfare blitzkrieg we have ever seen.” (Pomerantsev, 2014) Pomerantsev suggests that they are “reinventing reality”, creating a mass hallucination that Russia then translates into political reality. In this interpretation, Russian politics is a scripted reality show which the Kremlin is now trying to export internationally (Pomerantsev, 2015).

Within this framework, Russia seeks to establish its own memetic narratives, such as the idea that pro-democracy rebellions lead to bad outcomes (Pomerantsev, 2019, 106).

Russia certainly has sufficient capability to wage information war. Following the Russian Revolution, the Bolsheviks engaged in external espionage and disinformation activities that became known as ‘active measures’ (Ajir and Vailliant, 2018, 72). There are frequent claims that Russia’s espionage is fundamentally different from the West, which makes sense insofar as it is a country with a distinct culture, different organizational structures, and access to different levels and forms of resources and personnel. However, like traditional warfare, information warfare has specific targets it seeks to achieve and common tools available to do so: propaganda, media manipulation, disinformation, etc. In practice, the application of these tools will follow similar tactical and strategic paths. Institutional culture and policy may influence the success of the player, but it does not change the nature of the game being played. This makes it difficult to see anything uniquely Russian about claims that, ‘their’ propaganda consists of four key elements: large budgets, modern media, high technical expertise, and abuse of the Western media’s lack of government control (Ajir and Vailliant, 2018, 74-77). What is unique about any of this? Other than the West’s, arguable, lack of state control over its media, none of it is distinctly different

from tactics employed by the USA or UK. Similarly, suggestions that Russia uses online cyber operations because it allows deniability (Libicki, 2017, 60), in no way distinguishes them from Western agencies.

Again, there are institutional and cultural differences that produce general methodological differences; one is that rather than direct, top-down control, there is a more nebulous system of instruction where broad guidelines are given and subordinates have freedom to interpret the best way to reach these goals (Galeotti, 2017). Russia also takes a wider view of intelligence operations as being in constant play in all areas, at all times, rather than compartmentalizing them into the responsibility of small, dedicated groups (Mazarr, 2019, 54). These differences in approach aside, the nature of the operations employed by Russia and the West do not have much to distinguish them. Histories of CIA operations outline the extensive networks of propaganda and manipulation that existed throughout the Cold War (Wilford, 2009). Some of these operations went deeply into areas of information manipulation that matched efforts made by their Soviet counterparts (Saunders, 2013). That the United States’ own ‘Active Measures Working Group’ was focused on countering Soviet Propaganda (Schoen and Lamb, 2012), in no way detracts from the numerous interventions, coups, assassinations, and other varied forms of ‘active measures’ that the US employed throughout the period (Blum, 2013).

It was precisely because the West displayed such skill in information warfare that Russia’s Chief of the General Staff, Valery Gerasimov, wrote an article in 2013 in which he warned that the information environment was changing, and that Russia would need to adapt to the new challenges posed by this more complex form of persistent conflict (Gerasimov, 2013). While this was clearly a message advocating a reaction to an existing threat, it was presented in Western media as the ‘Gerasimov Doctrine’ with the implication that it was a call

for Russia to initiate a new form of warfare (McKew, 2017; Roblin, 2018). This is a perfect example of how even defense-oriented reactions from Russia can be twisted to be framed as a form of aggression.

Pomerantsev wrote that Russia was reinventing reality and supported the narrative that it was Russia that, “blurs the line between war and peace, resulting in a state of permanent conflict that is neither on nor off.” (2019, 85) However, in a critical review of Pomerantsev’s work the journalist Mark Ames pointed to the fact that the ‘scripted reality’ only came to Russia in the wake of the election victory of Boris Yeltsin. This US-backed exercise in political manipulation set the grounds for the influx of capitalism that gave birth to the oligarch-backed television stations that redefined the new Russian media (Ames, 2015). Pomerantsev himself highlights the fact that Russian intelligence services viewed concepts such as ‘Glasnost’ and ‘Perestroika’ as information viruses that the West had successfully promoted to undermine the USSR (Pomerantsev, 2019, 81). Whether or not this was justified, modern Russia continues to perceive itself as being under threat from the West. In 2015 Putin claimed that Western governments are working through NGOs to interfere in Russian politics (VoA, 2015), while in 2017 the Speaker for the Duma declared that between \$70-100 billion was being sent into Russia annually to fund Western political activism (RT, 2017). There are certainly a wide variety of overt actions being deployed against Russia by the US and its allies, from sanctions to cyberattacks targeting its power grid (Sanger and Perloth, 2019), which makes it reasonable to consider what form of covert activities might be ongoing.

This is the key question, not whether Russia engages in propaganda and information warfare, it most certainly does. Rather, it is important to clarify whether it is unique in doing so and whether it is reasonable to present Russia as being a special case in this regard. One of the many dangers in conflict situations

is that acts of aggression can lead to ever greater escalation. The ‘redline’ is a term used in conflict scenarios to denote the point at which reciprocal action must be carried out. In cyber warfare, the redline is typically where any sort of physical harm occurs. In information warfare the redline is far harder to delineate, which means it can be far harder to predict the point at which things might suddenly escalate (Ajir and Vailliant, 2018, 85). Allegations portraying Russia as a uniquely pervasive initiator of information warfare are, in effect, declarations that the redline has been crossed and that retaliation is warranted or even required.

III. The ‘Russian Disinformation’ Network

When you examine the authors of the books on Russian election manipulation, and several of the institutions releasing reports on the same issue, you soon find that there are linkages that create a core network based around key institutions. For example, Emerson Brookings (author) is a fellow at the Atlantic Council, as is Richard Stengel (author). Stengel previously served as US Under Secretary of State for Public Diplomacy and Public Affairs, overseeing the creation of the US Global Engagement Center (GEC) which commissioned the Park Advisors’ report on Russian disinformation. The GEC also has connections with the UK-based Integrity Initiative. Files released in a reported hack of The Integrity Initiative listed Peter Pomerantsev (author) as an advisor, and the same group is a subsidiary operation of the Institute for Statecraft, where Ben Nimmo, a researcher focusing on Russian online disinformation, worked as a fellow before joining the Atlantic Council. The Atlantic Council frequently collaborates with the ideologically conjoined Foreign Policy Research Institute where Clint Watts (author) worked as a fellow. Watts previously worked at the FBI under Robert Mueller, coordinator of the US investigation into Russian election interference, as did J.P.

Carlin (author).

The above is merely a brief example of the connections of several of the authors and organizations which have produced recent works on Russian disinformation and is by no means exhaustive. Of course, such connections should not be taken to suggest that individuals share the same worldview, rigidly follow the common beliefs of their host organizations, or that such organizations have monolithic structures that allow only one point of view. What it does suggest is that, on certain topics, there can be a superficial appearance of varied, individual opinions coming from neutral, unrelated experts. In actuality, there are frequently connections between these authors that significantly narrow down the range of opinion that they represent, i.e. rather than the full breadth of possible views they promote a more narrowly specific interpretation of the subject. Furthermore, the authors are often members of, or connected to, institutions which advocate specific ideological goals that have the *potential* to introduce some bias into the author's analysis.

A member of the public seeking to understand the subject of 'Russian election interference' might reasonably expect that, by buying four or five of the most popular books on the subject, they will encounter a balanced variety of viewpoints. Should they then find that the authors agree with one another completely on several key questions, our citizen might reasonably conclude that these matters are well-established facts and that they now have a good basic knowledge of the issue. In this case they would be dangerously wrong and this provides an example of how a 'memetic narrative' is generated, not through click-bait articles on social media, or viral memes that mock political candidates, but by pushing a tightly focused, narrative message through a small selection of individuals at a more intellectually rarified level, messages that reinforce one another and act to establish an officially sanctioned narrative that the average citizen will trust as being the 'accepted truths' of the well-educated person.

There are always two key dangers whenever a series of analyses adhere too closely to one another's core arguments. The first is that the lack of opposing views will result in weak argumentation and a lack of challenge to poor logic or faulty evidence. The other is that they will have a narrow focus that neglects important elements of contextual understanding. In the above instance, the ideology underpinning the institutions mentioned, and most of the works, is that of NATO which exists to promote the security and strength of Western European and North American states. In other words, they are not neutral but operate around a specific set of political priorities. The question is whether these priorities prejudice the work of these institutions or prevent their members from achieving neutral and unbiased assessment. Given that some of the previous authors openly state that they have been asked to help defend the USA from attack and to assist the US military (Singer and Brooking, 2019, 20), such concerns over neutrality are perfectly reasonable.

In the UK, a large amount of information warfare falls under the auspices of a recently formed 77th Brigade, a unit of the British military which has a strong focus on online and social media propaganda (Miller, 2018). In 2013, Edward Snowden, an employee of the US National Security Agency (NSA) leaked details of how his organization had spied on the American public. The leak also revealed the existence of the UK's Joint Threat Research Group, which acted as the state's tool for conducting more direct psychological operations (Greenwald and Fishman, 2015). However, these groups were merely that, tools of state, with no underlying ideological agenda.

The same cannot be said for a group which came to light due to hacking carried out by the group Anonymous in 2018. The files they released revealed that a group called the 'Integrity Initiative', funded by the UK's Foreign and Commonwealth Office (FCO) and linked to the Atlantic Council, had been engaged in the co-

vert creation of ‘clusters’ of journalists, academics and defense specialists in several European countries, with the goal of highlighting the threat posed by Russia and provoking an international response. (Klarenberg, 2018). According to the files, the group was run primarily by former members of the UK military and intelligence services and among other activities, promoted negative messages attacking UK opposition leader Jeremy Corbyn (Ferguson, 2018), a scandalous act given that the UK government admitted that the FCO had directly funded the Initiative (UK Parliament, 2018). Additional activities revealed in the leaked documents include a proposal from tech security company Lexfo to confidentially spread stories for the Initiative across hundreds of news sites, to edit Wikipedia pages to support their views, and to target, discredit and intimidate opponents (RT, 2018a). Another file states that the founder of the Rendon Group, the US PR firm who helped stage-manage the propaganda aspects of the Invasion of Iraq, gave a seminar to train its core members (Ferguson, 2019). Yet another focuses on a rapidly executed plan to, successfully, block the appointment of a Spanish military official deemed to be too soft on Russia by sending a flurry of disparaging tweets and editorials from cluster members (Klarenberg, 2018).

Even today, coverage of these activities in the UK and USA is incredibly scant. This failure of major press outlets to cover the Integrity Initiative revelations in any meaningful way, while dedicating considerable space to allegations of Russian information warfare (RT, 2018b), shows how a lack of contextual information can shape narratives portraying Russia’s aggressive use of disinformation versus a purely passive Western response.

IV. The RussiaGate Narrative

Perhaps the most persistent element of the ‘Russian disinformation’ narrative has been the allegation that Russia colluded with Donald

Trump to secure the 2016 US Presidency. At its earliest stages this narrative gained strong support from a US government report that stated, “We assess with high confidence that Putin ordered an influence campaign in 2016.” (Sanger, 2017) Of course, “high confidence” is a loaded term. In US intelligence the measure of conviction can be either neutral or one of three degrees of positive or negative belief. “High confidence”, therefore, is simply the mid-ground between a slight inclination and near certainty (DNI, 2015). In other words, it leaves ample room for backtracking, something that many elements of the US media may have desired when after more than two years the Mueller Investigation closed with a statement that it, “did not establish that members of the Trump Campaign conspired or coordinated with the Russian government in its election activities.” A common pattern during this period was for these outlets to print salacious headlines linking Trump to Russia only to later walk it back, or switch to a new claim, once their story proved to be baseless (Taibbi, 2019).

Some claimed that the hacking of the Clinton campaign provided more significant evidence of Russian manipulation (Nemr and Gangware, 2019, 18), yet, even from the beginning there were significant weaknesses in the case being made for Russian involvement in these leaks (Biddle, 2016). One problem is that it is incredibly hard to attribute the identity of hackers and US intelligence clearly had the capability to simulate evidence of Russian involvement (Zetter, 2017). One of the early pieces of ‘evidence’ was Cyrillic text left within a file, another involved the suggestion that one of the world’s top hackers forgot to use basic anti-measures, allowing US intelligence to detect his real street address and identify it as belonging to a Russian intelligence officer (Poulson and Ackerman, 2018). In general, the evidence on hand was either circumstantial or required trusting the neutrality of US intelligence agencies.

Frequently, when looking at evidence pro-

vided in support of the anti-Russian narrative, you find that the sources are groups with a preexisting anti-Russian bias, such as the RAND report which used the, decidedly anti-Russian, Atlantic Council's Digital Research Laboratory as the source for much of its data (Mazarr et al. 2019, 91). The same thing occurs when you examine CrowdStrike, the security firm which provided the initial link between the alleged Clinton hacks and Russia (Marwan, 2017). It's founder, Dmitri Alperovitch, also happens to be a senior fellow at the Atlantic Council where fellow Ukrainian Viktor Pinchuk runs the 'Ukraine in Europe Initiative' aimed at building international support for strengthening Ukraine's security, and preserving its territorial integrity (PF, 2020).

None of this rules out the possibility that Russia did, in fact, carry out hacking activities; all major states engage in such activities to some extent and Russia, like Ukraine, is home to some of the world's best hackers. What it does suggest is that the evidence for these acts must be weighed carefully with due consideration given to the biases of those involved. It should also be noted that former UK ambassador Craig Murray has explicitly stated that he acted as a conduit between the person who leaked the information from the Clinton data-breach and Wikileaks, that the person in question was a DNC insider, and that no hacking of any kind was involved (Goodman, 2016).

The final element in the trinity of 'Russian interference' claims is that Russia used online social networks to influence voters in both the US election and the Brexit election throughout 2016. The primary target of these claims was the Internet Research Agency (IRA) an online quasi-news service that was founded by Evgeny Prigozhin, a wealthy Russian with ties to the Kremlin. Even before the 2016 election, the IRA had been identified as pushing pro-Kremlin news articles and commentaries on social media (Seddon, 2014). Leaked documents from the organization show that one of its motivations was to address a perceived bias against

Russia in international media (Chen, 2015), however, in practice it seemed to place more attention on providing domestic PR for the Russian government. So far, there has been no evidence of direct control from the Kremlin and given the disaggregated nature of the Russian political system, the Russian state may not have had the ability to reign in the IRA's activities had it wanted to (Mazarr et al. 2019, 65). During the election it was frequently claimed that the IRA attempted to promote stories supporting Donald Trump, and that it was a key distributor of 'fake news'. The reality was that it promoted stories supporting and attacking both candidates, and the stories it used came primarily from US sources (Moshirnia, 2019, 99). In fact, some of its most popular stories frequently came from sources such as the Washington Post, Fox News, New York Times, and Reuters (Mazarr, 2019, 69-77).

When it was shown that it had not acted solely to promote pro-Trump messages, some claimed that the IRA's real goal was to spread distrust in the American political system (Mazarr et al. 2019, 59). Such claims must be weighed against the financial benefits the IRA received from promoting these 'click-bait' articles. In essence, the more controversial the messages they posted, the more money they were likely to make. During the same election period, similar money-oriented schemes were being run by teenagers in Macedonia, an entrepreneur in California, an intern for a US senator, and science students in Georgia. The vast majority of social media accounts run by the IRA, 97.5%, had few followers and little measurable influence (Hindman and Barash, 2018, 5-7). Most Americans likely scrolled past only a small number of IRA-generated posts during the entire campaign, with their social media impressions dwarfed by the billions of daily impressions generated each day (Stengel, 2019, 197; Nembr and Gangware, 2019, 18). Given that the IRA spent only \$100,000 dollars on Facebook and Twitter advertising it is hard to imagine how it could have generated any major

impact, especially when 2020 Democratic candidate Michael Bloomberg expended almost \$1 billion without significantly altering his campaign's success (Mazarr et al. 2019, 95).

The IRA was also accused of meddling in Brexit despite only generating 97 cents worth of advertising. A RAND study found that there was little evidence of Russia conducting more than minimal activity, and this producing no significant influence (Mazarr et al. 2019, 151, 191). Despite this, the interference claims persist, many of them relying on superficially dramatic statistics such as the claim that the IRA sent 2.2 million tweets in the last three months of the campaign (Singer and Brooking, 2019, 144). Numbers like this sound large until you realize they are just 0.004% of all tweets during that period (Hindman and Barash, 2018, 43), in other words a tiny fraction of the output from the 8-17% of Twitter accounts that are bots spamming similar click-bait messages (Chung, 2017).

The RAND study made clear that there was little hard evidence of Russia having any actual influence on elections (Mazarr et al. 2019, xi-xiii). Based upon this, the report suggested that Russian aims may have been to provoke a self-harming, excessive response from Western governments (Mazarr et al. 2019, 30, 104). They also noted that if the campaign had been to boost Russia's own popularity it could be considered a failure, given the significant decline in American attitudes toward the country compared to five and ten years previously (Mazarr et al. 2019, 174). The report effectively asks us to believe that Russia's so-called 'masters of reality' were both so ineffectual in their manipulation that its primary result would be the demonization of their country and harsh sanctions being placed against it, yet also prescient enough to know that the USA would engage in a witch-hunt so extreme as to constitute a form of self-harm. If Russia were truly preeminent in disinformation, there are other narratives which should have arisen and yet did not. Once the Russia-

Gate narrative failed to achieve its political objectives, the focus shifted to further alleged corruption by Trump involving Ukraine. Had Russia truly possessed such broad and powerful information war capabilities, this 'Ukraine-Gate' might have taken a different form, focusing instead on prior, documented efforts of Ukrainian politicians to work with the Democrat party to hinder Trump's campaign (Olearchyk, 2016; Vogel and Rosenberg, 2017). These activities never became a large-scale scandal though, being passed off instead as further evidence of Russian disinformation (Barnes and Rosenberg, 2019).

In March 2020 the case brought by the US government against the IRA was dropped when the IRA's representatives demanded to see the evidence against them. In fact, the case was requested to be removed 'with prejudice' by the prosecutors themselves, meaning it could never be tried again in US courts (Benner and LaFraniere, 2020). Yet, when one element of the Russian narrative declines another will arise. The outbreak of the Corona pandemic in early 2020 might have been seen by some as a reason for the world to come together in mutual aid, however, within a week of the IRA case being dismissed, stories began to appear in the Western press accusing Russia of using the pandemic to spread disinformation and panic in the West (Emmott, 2020).

A strong and persistent campaign exists to create a narrative of Russia as a threat to the West and as the primary distributor of online disinformation. Whether Russia is guilty of such claims is not the question this paper seeks to answer. Instead, it asks whether the case against Russia is presented in a neutral, contextualized manner. At present, there is little evidence of such an approach being taken in many Western studies of modern-day disinformation and information war. The nature of the selective bias involved in such analysis can be further highlighted by comparing coverage of the information operations of another non-Western state.

V. The Case of Israel

In 2016 the director general of the Israeli Ministry for Strategic Affairs and Public Diplomacy announced that she intended to “flood the internet” with content that would promote ‘hasbara’, the uniquely Israeli form of propaganda (AP, 2016). A previous head of the same ministry had stated that,

“One of the principles for success is keeping our methods of action secret...Since most of the ministry’s actions are not of the ministry, but through bodies around the world who do not want to expose their connection with the state, we must protect the information whose exposure could harm the battle.” (Knesset, 2017)

Because of such secrecy it is hard to know what “bodies around the world” this might be referring to, however, even utilizing its home-grown assets Israel can field a considerable army of online influencers. The Prime Minister’s office recruited more than 500 students at Israel’s universities to act covertly as propagandists on social media networks in return for scholarships (Ravid, 2013). This was following a previous call from the National Union of Israeli Students offering scholarships to its 300,000 members if they joined the online efforts to alter international perception of Israel (NUIS, 2012). More recently, participation in similar efforts was broadened using dedicated applications like ‘Act.il’, a social networking tool which, until 2022, coordinated responses to perceived negative treatment of the Israeli state on social media. Founded by former Israeli intelligence agents, the app targeted both mainstream news outlets and American politicians (Nathan-Kazis, 2017). The app sent out alerts to its 14,000 members warning them when a message deemed anti-Israel appeared online and encouraged them to do what they could to reduce the message’s impact or replace it with a pro-Israel alternative. Their own di-

rector claimed they were successfully able to promote the Israeli point of view in 85% of cases (Ben Yosef, 2018). This was a clear effort to establish a narrative around international perceptions of Israel and the app’s own website laid out the specific themes of this narrative: Israel is a diverse state, Israel is not an apartheid state, Hamas is evil, and political campaigns against Israel are a threat to freedom of speech (Act.il, 2020).

Links between Israeli state intelligence and private firms engaged in information war and psychological operations are not uncommon. Black Cube, the private business established by former member of Mossad, the Israeli foreign intelligence service, became more famous when it was revealed that they had been used by disgraced Hollywood mogul Harvey Weinstein to gather compromising information on his accusers. The company was also suspected of attempting similar activity against officials in the Obama Administration who were involved in the Iranian nuclear negotiations (Farrow, 2018). Israel’s military-intelligence agency, Aman, runs a sub-division known as Unit 8200 that specializes in cyber-warfare and has been credited with developing some of the world’s most advanced computer malware (Reed, 2015). Former members of this unit have gone on to establish several high-profile computer security firms such as Check Point and CyberArk (Choudhury, 2017). They also include Palo Alto Networks a firm that provides election security for state and local governments in the USA (Palo Alto, 2019). Another group, established by ex-Israeli intelligence officers, is Psy-Group which offered proposals to the Trump election campaign that it could use fake identities to target voters, use social media to create division among opponents, and carry out opposition research on Trump’s opponents (Mazzetti et al, 2018; Psy-Group, 2016, 8). Finally, a group of Israeli contractors known as ‘Team Jorge’ were the subject of a major investigation in 2023 that revealed that they had used hacking, sabotage and disinformation to

meddle in more than 30 elections around the world (France 24, 2023).

It is reasonable to imagine that, had Russia been found to have dedicated apps and a network of university students promoting its agenda covertly on social media, that if firms established by former Russian intelligence officers were involved in US election security, if other firms run by former Russian intelligence had been in discussions with the Trump campaign to influence the election process, and if other Russian firms had meddled in dozens of elections across the globe, it would have received considerable attention. The fact that these concerns about Israel are left almost entirely unaddressed by the vast majority of the previously mentioned books on election manipulation, is another example of how a lack of context can help to create a memetic narrative.

VI. Responding to Russia

The concept of ‘data localization’ involves cutting off segments of the internet from outside influence or control. Some see it as a form of ‘Balkanization’, intended to place the flow of information under the strict control of authoritarian regimes as seems to be the case in China’s use of the Great Firewall (Singer and Brooking, 2019, 89). However, for some states it can be argued that it is driven as much by a fear of a lack of control, as it is a desire for more complete control. Russia has introduced plans to create its own, self-contained internet that would operate independent of Western restrictions (Reuters, 2019). Such restrictions could include throttling the flow of data into Russia, or quarantining Russia sites from other sections of the internet. Even if they are not directly isolated or restricted by the West, there are other concerns Russia must take into account.

In China the government attempts to ‘harmonize’ its internet population by ensuring everyone follows the same pre-approved messaging (Singer and Brooking, 2019, 96). Similar

patterns can be seen emerging in the West where restrictions on free expression are steadily increasing year by year, masked as attempts to combat ‘fake news’, ‘disinformation’, and ‘extremism’. Some of the proponents of the Russia narrative claim that Russia seeks to establish a post-truth world in which they can more easily influence Western society. They declare that “fact, after all, is a matter of consensus,” without which, “fact becomes a matter of opinion” (Singer and Brooking, 2019, 127). Fact is neither consensus nor opinion, it is a truth that stands outside of human groupthink or passing inclination, and which can be reached only through objective assessment. Yet, it seems that the supporters of the narrative would prefer that we relinquish our rational capabilities and instead succumb to the “intelligence of crowds” guided by a cadre of experts (Watts, 2018, 219). These experts would, in this instance, be those who promote the West’s approved narrative. Many Russians, including tech entrepreneur Igor Ashmanov, increasingly feel that this includes the major social media companies whose strong ties to Western states compromise their neutrality. Ashmanov sees Google, Facebook and Twitter as ideological weapons aimed at Russia, with profit only a secondary goal (Pomerantsev, 2019, 82). This might appear somewhat conspiratorial, yet, in 2018 Facebook announced that it would begin working with the Atlantic Council to counter online disinformation (Facebook, 2018). In fact, it went so far as to hire former Atlantic Council Russian specialist Ben Nimmo as its “global threat intelligence strategy against influence operations” (Nimmo, 2021).

There is clearly a question of how concerned such businesses are with any notion of ‘truth’. Twitter’s efforts to purge millions of fake accounts saw a 21% drop in its stock due to the sudden reduction of customer accounts, while there is evidence that YouTube promotes extreme content to increase the ‘clicks’ that drive its revenue (Nemr and Gangware, 2019, 32-34). For both firms, higher user numbers

and more attractive content will always be more fundamental to their business model than ‘truth’, which means that any truth they promote will be malleable and based upon the returns it offers. In 2019 the actor Sasha Baron Cohen addressed the Anti-Defamation League, saying, “all this hatred and violence is being facilitated by a handful of internet companies that amount to the greatest propaganda machine in history.” (Pulver, 2019)

He wasn’t calling for these companies to be punished or blacklisted but, rather, for them to get on board with the correct narrative. Others have been more explicit, specifically pointing to the ADL and the Southern Poverty Law Centre as suitable advisors for helping to track online extremism (Meserole and Byman, 2019, 9). Again, it’s not a question of ‘truth’ but of the right version of truth.

According to Singer and Brooking, the heads of these tech giants are benign rulers, universally progressive and not particularly interested in politics (2019, 221), which would seem to be self-contradictory. The important thing, they argue, is that the “benign rulers” abandon any pretense that they are neutral platform providers and begin to treat authoritarian governments as adversaries (Singer and Brooking, 2019, 267). Some commentators feel that far too little is being done and condemn the tech giants’ failure to follow such requests and Western governments inability to enforce compliance (Watts, 2018, 276), while others suggest that a time may soon come when these corporations will “promise to safeguard human rights online.” (Pomerantsev, 2019, 26)

Tech-government collaboration is already taking form in a multitude of ways, one of which is through the Global Internet Forum to Counter Terrorism, which sees Twitter, Facebook, Google and Microsoft, partnering with the UK’s RUSI and the US’s Brookings Institute to identify online disinformation and extremism and align industry experts with lawmakers (Nemr and Gangware, 2019, 40-44). Others encourage the tech companies to use

copyright law to strip any imagery being used for what they deem unacceptable purposes, (Moshirnia, 2019, 150), to completely remove groups promoting such material from their networks, and for governments to work to build stronger ties with both new and fringe social media companies so that targeted groups cannot move to other platforms of expression (Nouri et al, 2019, 18).

As early as 2019 Russia’s Foreign Minister Sergei Lavrov, spoke of how, “an atmosphere of hostility and mistrust is fueled around Russian media outlets in many countries,” citing the example of a UK-hosted ‘Global Conference for Media Freedom’ which banned Russian journalists and diplomats from attending (TASS, 2019). Following the invasion of Ukraine in 2022 the EU Council banned the broadcasting of any content from Russia’s RT and Sputnik media channels and imposed sanctions on several Russian journalists. This was later expanded to include many more television and print media outlets, and a wider range of journalists. Numerous social media companies, including Twitter, Instagram, Facebook, YouTube, Tiktok, the Apple Store, and Spotify, also placed restrictions on access to Russian media. Google also altered its search algorithms to demote results from Russia media, causing a 90-95% drop in their traffic (MoFA, 2024).

In response to this, the European Federation of Journalists criticized the censorship as a danger to the democratic guarantees that protect freedom of expression (EFJ, 2022). However, this response effectively took claims of Russia media bias at face value and simply argued that there were better policy responses that heavy-handed censorship. They did not include the possibility that the vast breadth of Russian media might also include a large amount of honest and factual alternative news or opinions, or that it might act as a counterbalance to disinformation produced by the West. Nor did it raise any question regarding whether Western media channels should receive censure for any inaccurate or propagandistic news which they

have produced. In effect, the Western states have effectively managed to cripple Russia's ability to tell its side of a complex and contested story, leaving Western audiences with no option but to trust that Western news sources will be completely free from any political, ideological, or emotional bias of the kind they see as being pervasive in Russia. In the run up to the 2024 US presidential elections, US government sources have once again accused Russia of election interference (Dixon, 2024), leaving the possibility open that such accusations and the sociopolitical impact will become a cyclical affair.

VII. Conclusion

That the narrative of Russian disinformation and manipulation has broad appeal is understandable. In 2016, Trump's election and the Brexit vote left almost 50% of both the USA and UK deeply dissatisfied with the political climate of their country. By tapping into these emotions and providing a clear, external enemy for people to channel their feelings of bitterness and powerlessness against, the narrative offered the comforting belief that the election losses were largely a result of outside interference and that once this interference was removed the proper patterns would reestablish themselves.

That the narrative also perfectly served the core aims of influential groups like the Atlantic Council, NATO, the Integrity Initiative, etc. is hardly simple coincidence but rather the result of deliberate construction, via a steady stream of books, articles, and reports portraying the issue in a heavily one-sided fashion, lacking important context about the capabilities and activities of other states. This is not to suggest that states like Russia are blameless. Their disinformation and covert psychological operations are as potentially harmful to international peace and stability as those of any other country and deserve to be highlighted and condemned where they distort truth for political aims.

However, such critiques are, if done solely in a one-sided manner, inherently dangerous to the welfare of the countries which produce them. They invariably increase tensions between the states involved, offering justifications for reprisals that invite a like response and threaten a circle of escalation. They also represent a failure to generate a full and truthful understanding of the environment in which these actions occur, leaving us unaware of what our own capabilities may be, what actions have been taken in our name, and whether the claims of opposing states are in any way justified. Finally, they generate calls for greater policing of the global information commons, a shared repository of information that represents humanity's greatest step toward a truly liberating capacity for communication and access to knowledge. Entrusting control of this resource to a select cadre of governments, and profit-oriented corporations with bias toward those same governments, is unlikely to sustain the vital elements of neutrality and open-access that have made the internet so important to our civilizational growth.

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